

INFLUENCE OF SOWING SCHEMES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUNFLOWER VARIETIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article examines and analyzes the influence of the planting scheme on the development of sunflower plants. In this case, the processes of germination, star formation, flowering, basket formation, and ripening of sunflower varieties were studied by developmental phases compared to the standard variety. It has been established that the ripening period of sunflower accelerates with increasing feeding area..

Today, due to the increasing global demand for vegetable oil, there is a growing trend in the production of main oilseed crop seeds. Due to its high nutritional value and dietary suitability, vegetable oil replaces animal fats in human diet. In leading sunflower-producing countries, special attention is paid to increasing seed yield and quality through the development and application of advanced soil conditions, varietal characteristics, planting schemes, and cultivation technologies. Large-scale measures are being implemented in our republic to further develop agriculture and fully meet the population's needs for food, vegetable oil, and other agricultural products.

According to V.I. Filin, E.A. Sultanov [3] with a plant density of 30, 40, and 50 thousand plants/ha, of the 11 studied sunflower genotypes, the most early-ripening varieties were the Rodnik (P-453) and Kuban 371 (106-108 days) varieties. The vegetation period of the "Printasol" and "Rigasol" hybrids was 110-112 days, SF-270, Eurasol, SF-187, C-270, and Ikarsol-116-121 days, and Optisol and Don Jose-124-127 days. The Rigasol hybrid (without fertilizer application, a yield of 2.74 t/ha was obtained, which is 1.59 t/ha higher than the Rodnik variety and 1.2 t/ha higher than the Kuban hybrid) was recognized as the most productive.

Loshkomoynikov I.A., Puzikov A.N. [2] note that increasing sunflower plant density leads to plant stem growth and increased oil content in seeds, but reduces basket diameter and 1000 seed weight. For the confectionery sunflower variety in the Omsk region, the optimal

plant density is 20-30 thousand plants/ha. To obtain the maximum amount of oil, the number of oilseed sunflower seedlings should not exceed 70 thousand units per hectare.

In the experiments of T. Azizov, I. Anarbayev, S. Tukhtayeva [1] and other scientists, good results were obtained when sowing sunflower with 70-90 rows, bush spacing 25-30 cm. When using a pneumatic seeder, seed consumption was 6-8 kg per hectare. After seed germination, thinning was carried out with the condition of leaving 3.5-4 plants per 1 m². It states that the plant density of sunflowers is 35-40 thousand.

In our experiments, the influence of feeding area on the development duration of sunflower varieties was significant. The data obtained from the research results are presented in Figure 1. According to the obtained data on the duration of the developmental phases of sunflower varieties, seed germination occurred simultaneously on the same day in the experimental varieties "KK-1," "KK-60," and "KK-52," and only in the KK-60 variety, germination occurred 1 day earlier compared to other varieties, as the KK-60 variety is early-ripening.

In the 60x20-1 planting scheme, the "KK-60" variety germinated in 6 days, the duration of the star formation phase was 32 days; basket formation was 42 days; flowering was 37 days, and the duration of the ripening phase was 84 days. It was established that ripening takes 81 days with a planting scheme of 60x25-1, and 83 days with a planting scheme of 60x30-1. In variants with a large feeding area, early maturation of the harvest was observed by 3 and 4 days. This pattern was also observed in other experimental varieties.

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In this experiment, the control variety "KK-1" was distinguished by its late ripening. According to the experimental sowing schemes in the following sequence, delays of 12, 12, and 8 days were observed for the "KK-60" variety, and for 7, 6, and 5, and 5 days for the "KK-52" variety.

Figure 1. Duration of the developmental phases of sunflower varieties

As a result of the research, it was established that the ripening period of sunflower plants accelerates with an increase in the feeding area and, according to the variants, the ripening period is 3-4 days earlier in the "KK-1" variety, 2-3 days earlier in the "KK-60" variety, and 2-3 days earlier in the "KK-52" variety. Among the varieties studied in the experiment, the "KK-60" variety proved to be more early-ripening compared to the experimental varieties and matured 11-13 days earlier..

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